

Synthesis of Quinolino Oxazoles as Optical Brighteners

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A few 2-aryl and 2-heterocyclic substituted quinolino (3 : 4) oxazoles have been synthesized by condensing the substituted 3-amino-4-hydroxy quinoline with aromatic and heterocyclic carboxylic acids employing polyphosphoric acid as cyclodehydrating agent. The U.V., I.R., mass and fluorescence spectra of some of these compounds have been presented for characterization.

PYRIDINE and quinoline derivatives are good optical brighteners exhibiting blue fluorescence and these are also stable to hypochlorite¹. 2-Amino-3-cyano-7-(dimethylamino)-quinoline and its derivatives show an intense blue fluorescence in day light and brighten synthetic fibres². 7-Hydroxy-3-benzoxazolo quinoline was reported to be strongly fluorescent³. In view of the established fluorescent properties of 3-oxazolo quinoline derivatives it was thought interesting to synthesize quinoline (3 : 4) oxazoles to investigate their optical brightening properties.

Earlier 2-aryl quinolino (3 : 4) oxazoles were prepared by heating the 3-amino-4-hydroxy quinoline with respective aromatic acid anhydrides in moderate yields⁴.

In the present investigation, polyphosphoric acid is used as cyclodehydrating agent for the synthesis of quinolino (3 : 4) oxazoles. For the purpose of synthesizing the title compounds—2-methyl-3-amino-4-hydroxy quinoline and 2, 8-dimethyl-3-amino-4-hydroxy quinoline were condensed with aryl and substituted coumarin-3-carboxylic acids and terephthalic acid to get the corresponding 2-substituted quinolino (3 : 4) oxazoles.

The 3-amino-4-hydroxy quinolines are prepared following the procedure reported earlier⁵ improving

The above compounds have been characterised by U. V., I. R., mass and fluorescence spectral data.

U. V. Spectra :

The U. V. spectrum of the compounds have been recorded on Beckmann DK 2A spectrophotometer using dioxane as the solvent. The compounds exhibited two main regions of absorption around 340 ± 20 nm and 280 ± 10 nm, characteristic of coumarinyl substituted quinolino oxazoles.

The fluorescence spectra for all the compounds are measured on Beckmann DK 2A spectrophotometer

using dioxane as the solvent. The results are tabulated in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	2-(substituted) quinolino (3 : 4) oxazoles	max absorption nm	max emission nm	Difference	Colour observed
<i>9-Methyl quinolino (3 : 4) oxazoles</i>					
1.	2-(<i>p</i> -Toluyyl)	331	363.5	32.5	Violet
2.	2-(6'-Methyl-3'-coumarinyl)	361	458	97	Blue
3.	2-(8'-Methyl-3'-coumarinyl)	355	457	102	Blue
4.	2-(5',6'-Benzo-3'-coumarinyl)	392	483	91	Green
5.	2-(6'-Bromo-3'-coumarinyl)	365	462	97	Blue
6.	2-(3'-Coumarinyl)	359	458	99	Blue
7.	<i>Bis</i> -1',4'-(9-methyl-quinolino(3 : 4) oxazolo)benzene	352	406	54	Violet
<i>7,9-Dimethyl quinolino (3 : 4) oxazole</i>					
8.	2-(Phenyl)	337	363	26	Violet
9.	2-(<i>p</i> -Toluyyl)	337	362.5	25.5	Violet
10.	2-(Benzyl)	326.5	363	36.5	Light violet
11.	2-(2'-Naphthyl)	345	372	27	Intense violet
12.	2-(3'-Coumarinyl)	356	461	105	Blue
13.	2-(8'-Methyl-3'-coumarinyl)	362	459	97	Blue
14.	2-(6'-Methyl-3'-coumarinyl)	366	461	95	Blue
15.	2-(5',6'-Benzo-3'-coumarinyl)	391	485	94	Green
16.	2-(6'-Bromo-3'-coumarinyl)	363	469	106	Intense blue
17.	<i>Bis</i> -1',4'-(7,8-dimethyl quinolino (3 : 4) oxazolo) benzene	374	409	35	Violet

The information obtained from the fluorescence spectrum may be used in the evaluation of compounds as possible fluorescent brighteners for synthetic fibres, plastics etc. The fluorescent maxima of all these oxazoles have emission in the ideal range and therefore these compounds can be used as potential optical brighteners.

I. R. Spectra :

The I. R. spectra of these compounds have been recorded on Perkin-Elmer Model 137 in KBr. All the quinolino oxazoles exhibited a strong band around 1700 ± 25 characteristic of coumarin carbonyl group. In addition to that, peaks at 1550 to 1580 cm^{-1} , $1100 \pm 50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $1350 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ have also been found to be common, attributable

to >C=N ; $-\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$ and >C=N= of the oxazole system.

Mass Spectra :

Mass spectra were recorded on RMU-6L Mass spectrometer with inlet temperature ranging from 150° to 200° and an electron beam energy of 70 e.v. The major fragmentation pattern is the loss of $\text{M}^+ - \text{M} \cdot \text{H}^+ - \text{M} \cdot (\text{H} + \text{HCN})$ as observed in the case of alkyl substituted quinolines⁶. It was followed

by loss of carbon monoxide characteristic of coumarin moiety in the compounds. Molecular ion is the base peak.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected.

Preparation of 3-amino-4-hydroxy-2-methyl quinoline :

2.7 gm of 3-benzene azo-4-hydroxy-2-methyl quinoline was mixed with 4 gm of sodium dithionite ; 30 ml ammonium hydroxide ; 30 ml water ; 15 ml rectified spirit and refluxed for half an hour. The hot solution was filtered and cooled. 3-Amino-4-hydroxy-2-methyl quinoline crystallised out, m.p. 255° .

Preparation of 2-(substituted)-9-methyl quinolino oxazole :

A mixture of 3-amino-4-hydroxy-2-methyl quinoline (0.005 mole) and appropriate acid (0.005 mole) was added to the poly phosphoric acid maintained at 100° . The reaction mixture was heated first at $150-60^\circ$ for 2 hrs and then at $200-205^\circ$ for a further period of 2 hrs. The reaction product was neutralised with conc. potassium hydroxide solution to get the corresponding 2-substituted-9-methyl quinolino (3 : 4) oxazoles. Recrystallisation was done with appropriate solvents as given in Table 2. 2-Substituted-7,9-dimethyl quinolino oxazoles were prepared by the same procedure starting with 2, 8-dimethyl-3-amino-4-hydroxy quinoline and respective carboxylic acids.

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	2-(substituted) quinolino (3 : 4) oxazoles	M.P. °C	% Yield	Solvent of recrystallisation
<i>9-Methyl quinolino (3 : 4) oxazoles</i>				
1.	2-(3'-Coumarinyl)	250	60	Dioxane
2.	2-(Aryl)	177	65	Benzene
3.	2-(<i>p</i> -Toluyyl)	170	65	Benzene
4.	2-(6'-Methyl-3'-coumarinyl)	250	60	Dioxane
5.	2-(8'-Methyl-3'-coumarinyl)	240	60	Dioxane
6.	2-(5',6'-Benzo-3'-coumarinyl)	317	40	Dioxane
7.	2-(6'-Bromo-3'-coumarinyl)	278	60	Dioxane
8.	<i>Bis</i> -1',4'-(9-methyl quinolino oxazolo) benzene	245	60	Dioxane
<i>7,9-Dimethyl quinolino (3 : 4) oxazoles</i>				
9.	2-(Aryl)	178	65	Benzene
10.	2-(Benzyl)	273	65	Benzene
11.	2-(<i>p</i> -Toluyyl)	186	65	Benzene
12.	2-(2'-Naphthyl)	212	65	Benzene
13.	2-(3'-Coumarinyl)	265	60	Dioxane
14.	2-(8'-Methyl-3'-coumarinyl)	310	60	Dioxane
15.	2-(6'-Bromo-3'-coumarinyl)	248	60	Dioxane
16.	2-(5',6'-Benzo-3'-coumarinyl)	290	40	Dioxane
17.	2-(6'-Methyl-3'-coumarinyl)	257	60	Dioxane
18.	<i>Bis</i> -1',4'-(7,9-dimethyl quinolino (3 : 4) oxazolo) benzene	225	60	Dioxane

Preparation of Bis 1', 4'-(7, 9-dimethyl quinolino oxazolo) benzene :

A mixture of 3-amino-4-hydroxy-2-methyl quinoline (0.01 mole) and terephthalic acid (0.005 mole) was added to the polyphosphoric acid maintained at 100°. The reaction mixture was heated first at 140° for 2 hrs and then at 160° for a further period of 4 hrs. The reaction product was neutralised with conc. potassium hydroxide solution, recrystallised from dioxane.

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References

1. U. S. P., 2639, 990 ; C. P., 964, 861.
2. GRYCHTOL KLANS (BASF, A G) Germ. Offen. 2, 363, 459, (Cl. C07 D, 26 June 1975, Appl. P 2363, 459-5, 20 DCC 1973, 23 pl.
3. H. A. NAIK and S. SESHADRI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, **15(B)**, 506.
4. JAMES FRAZER and E. TILTENSOR, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 1781.
5. KUSUM DESAI and C. M. DESAI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, **5** 170.
6. SHELIA D. SAMPLE, DAVID A. LIGHTNER, OLE BUCHARDT and CARL DJERASSI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1967, **32**, 997.